

POSITION OF THE PRESS COUNCIL AS *QUASI RECHTPRAAK* (MOOT COURT)

JOKO SETIONO *

Doctoral Program in Law, Faculty of Law, Diponegoro University, Jl. Prof. Soedarto, SH., Tembalang, Semarang. *Corresponding Author Email: jokosetiono@students.undip.ac.id

LAZARUS TRI SETYAWANTA

Lecturer of Doctoral Program in Law, Faculty of Law, Diponegoro University, Jl. Prof. Soedarto, SH., Tembalang, Semarang.

JOKO SETIYONO

Lecturer of Doctoral Program in Law, Faculty of Law, Diponegoro University, Jl. Prof. Soedarto, SH., Tembalang, Semarang.

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the position of the Press Council as a Quasi Rechter (Moot Court). The method used is qualitative. The results of the research show that the Press Council functions to protect press freedom, which means that independence can be maintained, so that it functions in accordance with the objectives of holding press freedom. The Press Council has a mandate and mandate from Law No. 40 of 1999 concerning the Press to develop and maintain freedom or freedom of the press and improve the life of the national press and carry out the following functions: a). Protect the freedom of the press from interference by other parties. b). Conduct studies for the development of press life. c). Establish and supervise the implementation of the Journalistic Code of Ethics. d). Provide consideration and endeavor to resolve public complaints on cases related to press coverage. e). Developing communication between the press, society and government. f). Facilitating press organizations in drafting regulations in the press sector and improving the quality of the journalism profession. g). Registering press companies.

Keywords: Press Council, Journalism, Code of Ethics, Judiciary.

INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, the Press is regulated in Law Number 40 of 1999 concerning the Press (hereinafter referred to as the Press Law). In article 1, it is stated that the definition is:

"Social institutions and mass communication vehicles that carry out journalistic activities include seeking, obtaining, possessing, storing, processing, and conveying information in the form of writing, sound, images, sounds and images, as well as data and graphics and in other forms using print media, electronic media, and all kinds of available channels."

The press serves as a medium of information, education, entertainment, social control and as an economic institution. The function of the press that is the focus of this writing is the function of the press as an information medium or informative function, namely providing information to the general public in an orderly manner.¹

Independence and freedom of the press in Indonesia began to gain space after the reforms in 1998. Juridically, this was marked by the passage of Law Number 40 of 1999 concerning the Press to replace Law Number 21 of 1982 concerning the Subject of the Press which was considered repressive and shackled press freedom. Nonetheless, the legitimacy of press freedom granted by law also demands the professionalism of the responsible press. The national press is obliged to respect the norms of

religion and decency of society as well as the principle of presumption of innocence. A professional press has a workflow that is not simple and adheres to strict journalistic principles and codes of ethics, namely *fair*, *cover both sides*, *check and recheck*, objective, do not mix facts and opinions, and are not biased.²

Violations of journalistic principles and codes of ethics sometimes lead to disputes between the press and the party who is the object of reporting. On the one hand the press is a representation of the right to issue an opinion and the right to obtain information. The public, both as recipients and as subjects of information, often feels the presence of untruths in the news presented by the press. Reporting by the press often causes negative effects that must be borne by the public due to the arrogance of the press that interprets the freedom and freedom of the press too loosely or misses the limit.^{3,4}

The press council is a state institution, born on the mandate of the Press Law. Members of the Press Council consist of journalists and heads of press companies elected by their respective organizations. The Press Council carries out functions, including:

- a. protect the freedom of the press from interference by others;
- b. conducting studies for the development of press life;
- c. establish and supervise the implementation of the Code of Journalistic Ethics;
- d. provide consideration and seek the resolution of public complaints on cases related to press reporting;
- e. develop communication between the press, society, and government;
- f. facilitating press organizations in drafting regulations in the field of the press and improving the quality of the profession of citizenship;
- g. record the press company.⁵

The Press Council as a special institution formed to develop press freedom, its role is very important to be a regulator that provides legal protection to the press, including being a mediator for cases of press disputes. Through Supreme Court Circular Letter (SEMA) No. 13/2008, the Press Council was appointed as an expert witness in the trial of cases of conviction of journalists or editors related to press reporting. These expert witnesses from the Press Council are essential, not only for legal case resolution efforts, but also for the court's commitment to strengthening and protecting press freedom.⁶

In the legal higher education curriculum, press cases are limited to being introduced as a criminal law issue, or often referred to as Press Offenses or Press Crimes. As a result, not surprisingly, when there are legal cases involving the press, many parties bring the legal case directly through the criminal justice mechanism, by reporting it to the police for later hearing. Worse, the settlement of press law cases is resolved, not by the Press Law, but by other legal products.⁷

Problems that arise as a consequence of the dissemination of information carried out by the press should use the Press Law as a legal foothold in resolving problems about the substance of information made by the press, not using other laws, including the Criminal Code. Based on this, the author is interested in studying the position of the press council in the moot court.

DISCUSSION

Juridically, the Press Council was first formed in 1968 based on Law No. 11 of 1966 concerning the Subject of the Press signed by President Soekarno. The Press Council at that time functioned to assist the government in fostering the growth and development of the national press (Article 6 paragraph (1) of Law No.11/1966). The chairman of the Press Council *is ex-officio* the acting Minister of Information. Such a state of affairs lasted during the New Order Government. The position and function are the same: The Press Council serves as an advisor to the government, in particular the office of the Ministry of Information. The Minister of Information remains concurrently the Chairman of the Press Council. After Law No. 11 of 1966 was replaced by Law No. 21 of 1982 there was a change but in no way changed the position and function of the Press Council. The change that occurred was to mention the representation of various elements in the membership of the Press Council, which consisted of representatives of press organizations, representatives of the government, and representatives of the public. The previous law only explained "members of the Press Council consist of representatives of press organizations and experts in the field of the press".⁸⁹

A fundamental change only occurred in 1999. Through Law No. 40 of 1999 concerning the Press which was passed on September 23, 1999 and signed by President Bacharudin Jusuf Habibie, the Press Council changed to independent. Its function is no longer to be an adviser to the government but a protector of press freedom. Article 15 paragraph (1) states: "In an effort to develop the independence of the press and improve the life of the national press, an independent Press Council is established". Its members are democratically elected, consisting of: (a) Journalists elected by the organization of journalists; (b) The chairman of the press company elected by the organization of the press company; and (c) Public figures, experts in the field of press and or communication, and other fields selected by journalist organizations and press company organizations (Article 15 paragraph 3).

The function of the independent Press Council is no longer to be an advisor to the government, but to develop the independence of the press and improve the life of the national press. There was no longer any government interference in the establishment of an independent Press Council. The structural relationship between the Press Council and the government was severed, especially reinforced by the dissolution of the Ministry of Information by President Abdurrahman Wahid. There is no longer a government representative in the membership of the Press Council as it did during the New Order period.

Although the appointment of members of the Press Council remained through Presidential Decrees, there was no longer any government interference with the institutions or membership of the independent Press Council. The positions of Chairman and Vice Chairman of the Press Council are no longer listed in the Presidential Decree but are decided by all members of the Press Council in the Plenary Meeting.¹⁰

The Press Council is an independent institution that functions to develop press independence and improve the life of the national press. In Article 15 Paragraph (2) of Law Number 40 of 1999 it is said that the functions of the Press Council are as follows: Conducting studies for the development of press life; Establish and supervise the implementation of the Code of Journalistic Ethics; Give consideration and seek the resolution of public complaints on cases related to press reporting; Develop communication between the press, society, and government; Facilitating press organizations in drafting regulations in the field of the press and improving the quality of the citizenship profession; Record press companies.¹¹

Legal Position (*Rechpositie*) held by the Press Council

The independent Press Council has the mandate and mandate of Law No. 40 of 1999 concerning the Press to develop and maintain the independence or freedom of the press and improve the life of the national press and carry out the following functions: a). Protect the freedom of the press from interference from other parties. b). Conduct studies for the development of press life. c). Establish and supervise the implementation of the Code of Journalistic Ethics. d). Providing consideration and seeking the resolution of public complaints on cases related to press reporting. e). Develop communication between the press, society, and government. f). Facilitating press organizations in drafting regulations in the field of the press and improving the quality of the profession of citizenship. g). Record press companies.¹²

These seven functions are always carried out by the Press Council, protecting the freedom of the press which means keeping independence maintained, so that it functions in accordance with the purpose of holding press independence. There are three things that can diminish the meaning of press freedom; The first, third parties seeking to reduce, undermine or deprive the freedom of the press. Second, third parties who use press freedom only as masks for other purposes. Third, the press that uses press freedom unprofessionally and unethically.

The second function, in terms of the provision of assessments, all methods and means of assessment are possible to be carried out by the press council. The board conducted various surveys both conducted alone and in collaboration with other parties including with universities and media watches. The Press Council also conducts strategic analysis reviews, including to determine which steps are the priority scale and which are long-term steps. Then in carrying out the third function, namely establishing and supervising the implementation of the Code of Journalistic Ethics.¹³

The Press Council seeks to create a Code of Journalistic Ethics that can be used and apply to all journalists. In this case the press council has facilitated the creation of a Code of Journalistic Ethics by the press organization on March 14, 2006 which can apply to all such journalist organizations. Then the agreement was poured into the regulations of the Press Council. This means that the Press Council already has a reference to the Code of Journalistic Ethics that can be used as a reference for professional values.

The existence of the Press Council is expected to help overcome the problems of an unprofessional press. This institution is given the authority to draw up rules in the field of the press and supervise their implementation. Article 15 of Law No.40/1999 on the Press states that the establishment of the Press Council is an effort to develop press independence and improve the life of the national press. The Press Law mandates the Press Council to carry out seven functions, including those related to the protection of press independence, the assessment and development of the press, the implementation of the journalistic code of ethics, the resolution of press case complaints, the preparation of regulations in the field of the press, and the data collection of the press. Many activities of the Press Council have been held as an exercise of these seven functions.¹⁴

Since its establishment in 2000, the handling of press case complaints has become the main activity of the Press Council. In 2012 the Press Council received 470 complaints related to press stories and the behavior of journalists. As many as 86 percent of the press complained of were judged by the Press Council to be in violation of the Code of Journalistic Ethics. The establishment of an independent Press Council became the most important part in the change from a non-free press during the New Order period to a free press during the reform period.¹⁵

Law No.40/1999 on the Press unequivocally refers to the Press Council as an independent institution, not (anymore) subject to the ruling government or political parties. In such a position, the Press Council can play a role on the one hand in protecting press freedom to be guaranteed, on the other hand keeping press freedom from being abused by the press itself. The Press Council plays more of an enforcer of press ethics, a self-regulatory body in the field of the press, far from wanting to be a "monster of the press".¹⁶

The Press Council also receives and examines complaints about alleged violations of the journalistic code of conduct from all parties. Resolving complaints against alleged violations of the Code of Journalistic Ethics through the Right to Answer Mechanism, or Statement of Assessment and Recommendation (PPR). Then conduct education, training and socialization related to the journalistic code of ethics. However, in reality this role is not going well. It is noted that there are still many articles of Haatzai Artikelen rubber (hate speech) in the Criminal Code used by law enforcement officials to convict press personnel, including: Articles 154, 155, 156, 157, 160, and 162 of the Criminal Code. The use of articles of the Criminal Code to ensnare the press is an indication of the non-implementation of the Press Law, or it can also be said to be a formal marker of legal suppression of the press.^{17 18}

The Press Council is independent and there is no longer a government part in its management structure. The authority of the Press Council lies in the desire of editors and press media companies to respect the opinions of the Press Council and comply with the journalistic code of ethics as well as publicly acknowledge any wrongdoing. One of the functions that form the basis for the Press Council in carrying out the function of resolving disputes, including mediation, is sourced from article 15 paragraph (2) letter d of Law No. 40 of 1999 which states: "Providing consideration and seeking the resolution of public complaints on cases related to press reporting".

The presence of the Press Council since 1966 through Law Number 11 of 1966 concerning the Basic Provisions of the Press, at which time the Press Council functioned as an advisor to the Government and had a structural relationship with the Ministry of Information. Over time the Press Council continued to develop and finally had the latest legal basis, namely Law Number 40 of 1999 concerning the Press. From then on, the Press Council became an independent institution. The establishment of the Press Council is also intended to fulfill human rights, because the freedom of the press is included as part of human rights.

The Press Council has the authority to resolve journalistic disputes, it is emphasized in one of the functions of the press council as stated in Law Number 40 of 1999 in article 15 paragraph (2) letter d which states: "Providing consideration and seeking the resolution of public complaints on cases related to press reporting". The weakness of the Press Law is what must be corrected in order to become a *lex specialis* for the press world in Indonesia. It is also still a polemic that whether the Press Law is a *lex specialis* or not. The judicial system in Indonesia does not seem to be able to fully accommodate the implementation and restrictions imposed in international law related to freedom of the press and freedom of expression. In various court decisions related to defamation, it still appears that ethical issues have become the realm of law.

The Press Council, in researching and testing the quality of journalistic works, refers to eleven items of the Code of Journalistic Ethics, and its interpretation as a tool for analysis of ethical violations that occur. Eleven items of the Code of Journalistic Ethics confirm that Indonesian journalists:¹⁹

- 1) Be independent, produce accurate, immersive and non-bad faith news.
- 2) Take professional ways in carrying out journalistic duties.
- 3) Always test information, report falsely, do not mix facts and judgmental opinions, and apply the principle of presumption of innocence.
- 4) Does not make fake, slanderous, sadistic and obscene news.
- 5) It does not mention and broadcast the identity of the victim of a moral crime and does not mention the identity of the child who is the perpetrator of the crime.
- 6) Do not abuse the profession and do not accept bribes.
- 7) Have the right to refuse to protect sources who are not willing to be identified or whereabouts, respect the terms of the embargo, background information, and off the record in accordance with the agreement.
- 8) Not writing or broadcasting news based on prejudice or discrimination against a person on the basis of differences in ethnicity, race, color, religion, sex and language and not degrading the dignity of the weak, poor, sick, mentally handicapped. Or physically disabled.
- 9) Respect the rights of the source about his or her personal life, except in the public interest.
- 10) Immediately retract, correct and correct erroneous, and inaccurate news accompanied by an apology to readers, listeners or viewers.
- 11) Serves the right of answer and the right of correction in proportion.

Based on the items of the Code of Journalistic Ethics above, the Press Council identifies errors or violations of the code of ethics that occur, by assessing the intention of information dissemination, how to obtain information, testing of information sources, and its delivery (non-prejudiced, non-discriminatory, non-judgmental, not defamatory, not degrading, and always respecting privacy). The eleven items serve as guidelines for the Press Council in assessing, reviewing and reviewing public complaints that enter the Press Council, especially those related to Journalistic works.

In order to develop press independence and improve the life of the national press, the Press Council carries out functions including establishing and supervising the implementation of the Code of Journalistic Ethics, as well as providing consideration and seeking the resolution of public complaints on cases related to press reporting. In this context, the function of the Press Council is not to be a defender of the media. The task of the Press Council is to uphold the Code of Journalistic Ethics and protect the independence of the press.

In December 2010, the Press Council received 512 complaints: 144 direct complaints and 368 transluents; 48 cases of mediation, four cases by decision of the Press Council. The rest is by mail or direct communication with related parties. Apart from that, the Press Council also handles several cases of press ethics without any complaints from the public. The result of mediation and handling of cases carried out is a decision or recommendation that 80 percent states that the media or journalists violate the code of ethics in various forms.²⁰

The sanctions imposed by the Press Council for violations of the code of ethics are the loading of the right to answer accompanied by an apology, and the necessity to attend journalistic training for journalists or editors who violate the code of ethics. Of those, 95 percent were adhered to by the media or journalists, and few media outlets were unwilling to abide by the decisions or recommendations of the Press Council.

The Press Council in the previous period, namely the period 2007-2010, through the Commission on Public Complaints and Enforcement of Press Ethics, received a total of 1,185 complaints, most of which also concerned violations of the Code of Journalistic Ethics. Generally violated are Articles 1, 2, 3, and 4 concerning: Unbalanced, unprofessional, and judgmental reporting, as well as some broadcasting obscene news. Others violate Articles 9, 10, and 11, including not respecting the personal rights (privacy) of sources, not immediately correcting their false news, and not serving the Right to Answer in proportion.²¹

However, despite the name of the Press Council, this institution is not a council that merely always wins the press in any case under the pretext of upholding the freedom of the press. Based on its function to enforce and supervise the Code of Journalistic Ethics, the Press Council is a council of press societies that guarantees that people's rights are not trampled on by the press by taking refuge behind the concept of press freedom. It is not surprising, then, that the Press Council blames the media or journalists and in many cases requires the media concerned to contain the complainant's Right to Answer along with an apology to the party concerned and or the public.

The role of the national press is to convey information to the public, so that if there is misinformation related to the news, the main obligation of the press is to apologize to the public. The public is the most disadvantaged when the press contains misinformation. The Press Council has always sought a settlement through deliberation for consensus set forth in the peace statement. If deliberations do not reach consensus, the Press Council continues the examination process to make a decision. The decision of the Press Council is in the form of a Statement of Assessment and Recommendation (PPR) which is determined through the Plenary Meeting. Notice of Decision on Statement of Assessment and Recommendation from the Press Council shall be submitted to the parties to the dispute and shall be of an open nature.

Position of the Press Council as *Quasi Rechtpraak* (Moot Court)

The handling of criminal acts committed related to the press has its own uniqueness when compared to the handling of other criminal acts. Although there is no specific procedural law to enforce the law within the criminal scope of the press, there are certain procedures that must be passed. The uniqueness of the procedure for handling press crimes can be observed from the institutions involved in handling press law enforcement, the regulations and laws used, criminal elements that can be categorized to determine the existence of errors, prove criminal acts, and the flow of handling them.²²

The handling of press cases involves special institutions that are not found in law enforcement in other cases, both *ordinary crimes* and *extraordinary crimes*. The specific institution in question is the Press Council. According to the provisions of Article 5 paragraph (2) of Law Number 40 of 1999 concerning the Press, the functions of the Press Council include establishing and supervising the implementation of the Journalism Code of Ethics and providing consideration and seeking the resolution of public complaints on cases related to press reporting. However, if the case in question has been handled by the police, the Press Council will not handle the complaint.

The Press Council tries to apply the principles of kinship and deliberation to consensus in handling news cases. The complainant and the complaining media were found in one forum. Then as mediator the Press Council mediated the two parties to the dispute. If consensus is reached, it is then stated in

the Peace Statement of both parties. In general, in the closing of the Peace Statement plus a clause that the parties will not bring the case in question into the realm of law. If the press is unable to maintain its compliance with the Code of Journalistic Ethics, it does not rule out the possibility of criminalization of journalists.²³

Article 1 Paragraph (2) of the Complaints Procedure to the Press Council provides that the Press Council does not examine complaints that have been reported to the police or courts. Although a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) has been signed with the National Police, containing news cases that have been reported to the National Police, it is possible to mediate by the Press Council, the decision to continue or not to continue the case with legal proceedings remains in the hands of the whistleblower.

In practice, it is often found that the loading of the Right to Answer is considered to have not met the sense of justice or cannot solve the problem. Therefore, the parties can bring the news case through the mediation process at the Press Council. This is in accordance with the function of the Press Council to provide consideration and seek the resolution of public complaints on cases related to press reporting. If the consideration of the Press Council is not heeded, then there is an opportunity for the aggrieved party to file a lawsuit for compensation for the news. This means that the mechanism to be used is a civil justice mechanism, not a criminal one. Because the conviction of journalistic work using criminal articles in the Criminal Code, indirectly, is a form of denial of the principles of democracy and freedom of the press. In its advocacy, the Press Legal Aid Society (LBH) stated that criminal penalties to journalists or media companies clearly have an impact on the press community as a whole. The criminalization of journalistic work not only undermines press freedom, but also silences people's freedom and right to information.²⁴

The mechanism through the Press Law has been recognized, and even based on a number of legal considerations in the Constitutional Court decision, a press reporting case that is without or not initiated through the process of exercising the Right to Answer or until a settlement through the Press Council, is considered inconsistent with the Press Law and a lawsuit or conviction of the case is likely to be defeated. That is why, the Right to Answer mechanism is an important key to its legal position in a settlement of press coverage cases.²⁵

The existence of a right to answer application is the main thing that must be taken by the party who feels aggrieved by a news report. In this case the press is obliged to serve that right of reply. If the press does not fulfill the right to answer for the aggrieved party, then the aggrieved person can make a complaint to the Press Council. On complaints of parties who are not served the right to answer, the Press Council will mediate between the aggrieved party for the published news, and the press company.

If this mediation process does not obtain a solution to the disputed problem, the Press Council will hold a plenary session to issue a statement of assessment and recommendation on the journalistic work complained of. Furthermore, after obtaining a statement of assessment and recommendations from the Press Council, there are two possibilities that can be presented. If the assessment and recommendation state that there is no violation of the Code of Journalistic Ethics and compliance with journalistic work procedures, then the case is declared over. However, if on the contrary the judgment of the press council states that there is a violation of the Code of Journalistic Ethics in the journalistic work complained of, then recommendations in the civil and criminal channels can be followed up to law enforcement in the realm of litigation.

Compared to other judicial mechanisms, criminal justice is a much older mechanism in the resolution of press law cases, as it has been practiced since colonial times. There are a number of criminal articles that are often addressed to the press using the Criminal Code, including:

- 1) Articles of sow-in-awe of hatred (*haatzaai artikelen*), such as articles 154-157 of the Penal Code;
- 2) Contempt and defamation, articles 134, 136bis, articles 137, articles 207-209, articles 310, 311, 315 and 316 of the Criminal Code
- 3) Broadcasting false news, articles 171, 317 of the Criminal Code
- 4) Sedition, articles 160-161 of the Criminal Code
- 5) Violation of decency and decency, articles 282 and 533 of the Criminal Code.
- 6) Violation of state secrecy, articles 112-115 of the Criminal Code.

These criminal articles are also supplemented by a number of other articles in other laws such as the Law on Information and Electronic Transactions, such as the article on defamation through virtual media (article 27 paragraph 3 of the ITE Law). Although there are facts that press cases are brought through criminal justice mechanisms, recent developments in law and press freedom show that this mechanism is no longer necessary for solving press reporting problems.

Therefore, the position of the Press Council as *Quasi Rechtpraak* (Moot Court) is a solution to the settlement of press cases in Indonesia, although in this case it needs further study, especially in relation to criminal and civil justice.

In resolving press disputes that often occur between press personnel and other parties, the press council must be able to resolve disputes that occur using several settlement strategies, including the following:

1. Mediation

Empirically, the Press Council has become a mediator in disputes between the press as a herald and those who feel aggrieved by press reporting. As a further implementation of this function, in the organizational structure of the Press Council was established the Commission on Public Complaints and Enforcement of Press Ethics. Mediation by the press council is mediation outside the court process, and is voluntary or at the option of the parties. Thus the press council can carry out the function of mediation if the reporting party and the party who feels aggrieved as a result of being reported request or approve the Press Council to perform its functions.²⁶

2. Statements, Assessments and Recommendations (PPR),

Statements, Assessments and Recommendations (PPR) in the resolution of press disputes referring to the Press Law and the Code of Ethics of Journalists, the role of the Press Council is very important in the life of the press. The results showed that the role of the Press Council in resolving press disputes is to receive all reports and complaints, be it from the public, the government, or the press itself. In resolving press disputes that are reported or complained about, the Press Council uses a mediation mechanism. If no meeting point is reached between the two parties, the Press Council then issues a Statement, Assessment and Recommendation (PPR) submitted to both parties to the dispute.²⁷

3. Right to Answer Mechanism

The Press Council has always emphasized that people exercise their Right to Answer. Reference is written or recorded that the erroneous news was once refuted and straightened out. If there is no written or recorded reference, then the public and even the children and grandchildren of the person

or institution concerned will assume that the news is true, because it has never been refuted. Therefore, whenever there is adverse news, the Press Council advocates immediately the use of the Right to Answer in proportion.²⁸

4. Correspondence or telephony

The Press Council also resolves complaint cases by correspondence or telephon. The correspondence process is carried out if the complaint comes from an area far from Jakarta or is difficult to reach so that the direct mediation process is technically difficult or expensive. So the settlement is carried out by correspondence with the complainant and the complainant, which is usually complemented by telephony communication. This happens, for example, in cyber media that must immediately correct their news or delete news comments that cause controversy or harm certain parties.²⁹

5. Opinion Giving

Strictly speaking, Law No. 40 of 1999 concerning the Press regulates the criminal settlement of the press through the Right to Answer and the Right to Correction as stipulated in Article 5 paragraphs (2) and (3). If the Press Company does not implement the settlement mechanism as referred to in Article 5 paragraphs (2) and (3), then the party who feels aggrieved can follow the provisions of Article 18 paragraph (2), criminalizing the Press Company with a criminal penalty of a maximum of five hundred million rupiah. Those who feel aggrieved by news or press activities can take another route, namely making complaints to the Press Council. Furthermore, the Press Council will conduct an assessment and assessment of the complaint.³⁰

CONCLUSION

The press council serves to protect the independence of the press, so it functions in accordance with the purpose of holding press independence. The Press Council has the mandate and mandate of Law No. 40 of 1999 concerning the Press to maintain the independence or freedom of the press and improve the life of the national press and carry out the functions of: a). Protect the freedom of the press from interference from other parties. b). Conduct studies for the development of press life. c). Establish and supervise the implementation of the Code of Journalistic Ethics. d). Providing consideration and seeking the resolution of public complaints on cases related to press reporting. e). Develop communication between the press, society, and government. f). Facilitating press organizations in drafting regulations in the field of the press and improving the quality of the profession of citizenship. g). Record press companies.

Footnote

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